

ISic1152

I.Sicily inscription 1152

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140637

1. Θε (οῖς) □ Κα (ταχθονίοις) .
2. Πονπωνία
3. Μάξιμα
4. ἔζ (ησεν) □ ἔτ (η) □ μ'.
5. Κ[λ](αύδιος) Μ[έ]λισσος
6. τῆ ἰδίᾳ
7. συ [μ] βίω.
- 8.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492765

EDCS 39102309

PHI 140637

Bibliography

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